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Further analysis of a direct soft photon excess in $\pi^- p$ interactions at 280 GeV/c

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Abstract

In this Letter we present additional experimental characteristics of anomalous soft photon radiation observed in $\pi^- p$ interactions at 280 GeV/c in the CERN experiment WA91, together with a re-calculated ratio of the observed direct soft photon signal to the expected level of the hadronic inner bremsstrahlung, which is found to be 5.3 ± 1.0 . The other presented characteristics, energy dependence and angular distributions of direct soft photons, show the similarity of the observed signal to the expected hadronic bremsstrahlung behaviour.

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1. Introduction

It was shown 50 years ago that, from the theoretical point of view, the production of direct soft photons

in hadronic collisions at high energy is dominated by inner bremsstrahlung emitted by ingoing and outgoing charged hadrons participating in the reaction [1,2]. However, since the first experimental results on soft photon production in hadronic collisions started to appear, an excess of soft photons over the predicted level has been reported several times [3–5]. The excess photons which were dubbed as anomalous soft

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photons (ASP) were found to dominate the P_T range below 20 MeV/ c in the forward kinematic region ($y_{\text{c.m.s.}} > 1$). Reviews of the first experimental results and the attempts at theoretical explanations of the ASP phenomenon can be found in [6,7]. Currently, no theoretical explanation exists for the ASP photons in the P_T range below 10 MeV/ c where the effect is most prominent.

In Ref. [8], we published a paper on an excess of soft photons ($P_T \leq 20$ MeV/ c , $1.4 < y_{\text{c.m.s.}} \leq 5$) produced in $\pi^- p$ interactions at 280 GeV/ c . The main result of that Letter was presented in two forms:

- (i) a soft photon rate (after non-direct soft photon background subtraction), of $(9.8 \pm 0.4 \pm 1.5)\%$ per interaction;
- (ii) and a ratio of the observed direct soft photon signal to the expected level of the inner hadronic bremsstrahlung. The bremsstrahlung rate was calculated to be $(1.25 \pm 0.05 \pm 0.13)\%$. This resulted in a Signal/Bremsstrahlung ratio of 7.8 ± 1.5 .

Further study of the signal has been carried out with the aim of extracting more experimental characteristics of the ASP radiation using WA91 data. We report in this Letter the dependence of the radiation from $\pi^- p$ interactions at 280 GeV/ c on the photon energy and polar angle.

Meanwhile, the development of our Monte Carlo code has shown that the inner bremsstrahlung rate quoted in paper [8] was underestimated by a factor of about 1.4. Consequently, the ratio of the observed signal to the expected bremsstrahlung level decreases, but still remains anomalously high. Thus in this Letter, we give a corrected ratio of the observed soft photon signal to the re-calculated inner bremsstrahlung rate.

2. Photon selection and expected photon rates

Our results are based on the data of the CERN WA91 experiment. The data were collected in a special run designed for the study of inclusive soft photon production in $\pi^- p$ interactions at 280 GeV/ c . Minimum bias (interaction) triggers were collected. Of these 1.6×10^6 events with an interaction vertex located within the beam region inside the 60 cm

hydrogen target and having less than 8 charged tracks have been used in this analysis.

The apparatus and experimental method are described in details in [8,9]. Here we simply note that photons from $\pi^- p$ interactions in the OMEGA spectrometer were detected via the materialisation of the photon into an electron–positron pair in a 1 mm thick Pb sheet placed at a distance of 73 cm downstream of the target center. The e^+e^- were reconstructed as V^0 's from the digitizations produced in the downstream MWPCs using a modified version of the standard TRIDENT reconstruction program [10], which enabled reconstruction of tracks originating in the Pb sheet with momenta down to 40 MeV/ c . Only well reconstructed photons which were well separated from charged tracks were accepted for analysis: it was required that a distance from the γ apex to the nearest track in the x - y plane (perpendicular to the OMEGA magnetic field direction) was greater than 3 mm. For the calculation of the photon polar angle θ and the associated variable of transverse momentum P_T , we preferred, instead of the photon momentum direction determined from the e^+e^- pair, the more precise direction given by using the reconstructed interaction point in the target and the photon materialisation point in the lead sheet.

The main sources of soft photons in our experiment are known to be: (i) inner hadronic bremsstrahlung; (ii) photons from hadronic decays, and (iii) external bremsstrahlung (secondary radiation from e^+e^- pairs from photons converted in the material upstream of the lead sheet: target, target walls, Silicon detector, etc.). It was found that each of these three sources contributes about 10% of the observed soft photon rate. Other sources also were considered and found to give small yields: photon radiation from Dalitz pairs from π^0 , η and ω decays, knock-on electrons from energetic tracks, and spurious γ 's (V^0 consisting of hadronic tracks which nevertheless satisfy the photon selection criteria). These estimations were done using a Monte Carlo program which transports the particles generated by the FRITIOF code [11] (γ 's and Dalitz e^+e^- pairs included) through our experimental set up. The EGS4 code [12] was involved for the proper treatment of the e^+e^- pairs and photons. Expected background rates are shown in Table 1.

A generator of the inner bremsstrahlung photons was added to the FRITIOF code and the bremsstrahlung

Table 1

Calculated soft gamma yields ($0.2 < E_\gamma < 1$ GeV, $\theta < 20$ mrad). The quoted errors are statistical. The systematic errors for background calculations are estimated to be 10%, and for inner bremsstrahlung 5%

Source (see text for definitions)	Number of γ per event (%) corrected for conversion efficiency
(a) Inner bremsstrahlung	1.74 ± 0.03
(b) γ 's from hadronic decays	1.73 ± 0.03
(c) Dalitz pairs	0.07 ± 0.01
(d) Knock-on electrons	0.002 ± 0.001
(e) Spurious γ 's	$(1 \pm 1) \times 10^{-3}$
(f) Secondary γ 's	1.92 ± 0.04
Sum over sources (b) to (f) (full non-direct photon background)	3.72 ± 0.05

calculations were performed using the form suggested in Ref. [13]:

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d^3\vec{k}} = \frac{\alpha}{(2\pi)^2} \frac{1}{E_\gamma} \int \left(d^3\vec{p}_1 \cdots d^3\vec{p}_N \right. \\ \left. \times \sum_{i,j} \eta_i \eta_j \frac{\vec{p}_{i\perp} \vec{p}_{j\perp}}{(P_i K)(P_j K)} \frac{d\sigma^H}{d^3\vec{p}_1 \cdots d^3\vec{p}_N} \right), \quad (1)$$

where K and \vec{k} denote photon four- and three-momenta, P and \vec{p} are 4- and 3-momenta of charged hadrons, $\vec{p}_{i\perp} = \vec{p}_i - (\vec{n} \cdot \vec{p}_i) \vec{n}$, \vec{n} is the photon unit vector. $\eta = 1$ for the beam π^- and positive outgoing particles, $\eta = -1$ for target protons and negative outgoing particles, and the sum being extended over all charged particles.

The study of possible systematic errors of hadronic background and inner bremsstrahlung estimations was done varying the charged multiplicity of generated events, the input spectra of hadronic photons,² and testing the stability of the formula for the inner bremsstrahlung calculation (1) against the charged particle losses. It was found that the photon rates given in Table 1 remain stable within 5–10% with the MC variations listed above.

The photon reconstruction efficiency (selection efficiency included) was determined by implanting MC

² Variation of the accepted charged multiplicity affects background photon rates. Even with a fixed charged multiplicity, the photon spectra vary slightly (both, in shape and in rate) when varying the acceptance conditions for the charged tracks (rejecting low momenta and/or wide angle tracks).

photons (converted in the lead sheet to e^+e^- pairs and transported through the experimental setup using EGS) into the raw data of real events followed by a full reconstruction and analysis treatment. The efficiency was binned as a two-dimensional table over the photon energy and emission angle. The systematic error for the efficiency averaged over our kinematic domain was found varying parameters of the efficiency finding code and does not exceed 10%. This error dominates the systematic error of the real data photon rate.

We used the implantation technique to prove that the P_T measurement, based on the γ apex coordinate finding, is not distorted by multiple scattering. The P_T error comes mainly from the reconstruction error in the γ apex z coordinate, and was found to be ± 2.9 MeV/ c , with the θ accuracy of ± 5.6 mrad. As to the γ energy measurement, it was accurate to within 10 MeV. (All errors quoted in this paragraph are average and relevant to the photon energy range of 0.2–1 GeV.)

3. Signal of direct soft photons

The P_T spectrum of reconstructed photons emitted inside a cone of half angle of 240 mrad around the beam direction and with energy $0.2 < E_\gamma < 1$ GeV, corrected for reconstruction and conversion efficiency, is shown in Fig. 1 as full circles, the background spectrum in the same kinematic region obtained using our Monte Carlo code as described above, is shown by open circles, and the bremsstrahlung predictions by triangles. Here and in subsequent figures the errors plotted are statistical. As can be seen from the figure, the data follow well the expected P_T distribution of photons coming from the hadronic decay background above a P_T of 30 MeV/ c . In contrast to the presentation of [8], as a result of our MC development, we do not need any additional normalisation factor for the data and MC spectra at higher P_T to be in good agreement. For $P_T < 20$ MeV/ c a clear excess exists which rises towards small P_T . As can be seen by comparing Figs. 1(a), (b) with Figs. 1(c), (d), this excess is essentially concentrated in angles $\theta < 20$ mrad.

The ratio of photons in the kinematic region $0.2 < E_\gamma < 1$ GeV, $\theta < 20$ mrad to the number of interactions is $(12.9 \pm 0.4)\%$, having taken account of the photon conversion probability. The quoted error is sta-

Fig. 1. (a) P_T distribution for photons with energy $0.2 < E_{\gamma} < 1$ GeV, $\theta < 240$ mrad corrected for detection efficiency. "Data" means the experimental data, "BG" means the full non-direct photon background, and "Brems" stands for inner hadronic bremsstrahlung; (b) same with the background subtracted; (c), (d) same as (a), (b) but within interval $\theta < 20$ mrad.

tistical. The systematic error, mainly due to uncertainty in the reconstruction efficiency, is below 12% of the rate. Reducing the photon rate by the sum of non-direct soft photons yields (background contributions (b) to (f) of Table 1) we find that, in the defined kinematic region, the signal of the soft photons is $(9.2 \pm 0.4 \pm 1.5)\%$ per interaction.

The ratio of the observed signal to the expected inner bremsstrahlung is 5.3 ± 1.0 , thus confirming the ASP effect. The uncertainty in the ratio comes mainly from the efficiency corrections and the inner bremsstrahlung MC calculations.

4. Energy dependence

The spectra of soft photons corrected for the reconstruction and conversion efficiency, before and after subtraction of the non-direct γ background, are shown in Fig. 2 together with the predicted bremsstrahlung distribution (photons in the spectra are restricted to the interval of $\theta \leq 20$ mrad).

The spectra were fitted by a form

$$\frac{dN_\gamma}{dE} = A \left(\frac{E}{E_0} \right)^\alpha, \quad (2)$$

where $E_0 = 1$ GeV, with the following result for the fit parameters:

(a) Data (non-direct photon background subtracted): $A = (6460 \pm 540 \pm 1910) \text{ GeV}^{-1}$, $\alpha = -1.11 \pm 0.09 \pm 0.15$.

(b) Bremsstrahlung γ 's: $A = (1460 \pm 44) \text{ GeV}^{-1}$, $\alpha = -0.93 \pm 0.04$.

Systematic errors for the parameters A and α in the data fit were determined by scaling photon spectra from the data and hadronic background within the ranges of their systematic errors.

It appears therefore that the energy dependence of the observed soft photon signal agrees well with that of the bremsstrahlung, $1/E$.

5. Angular distributions

The distributions of the soft photons against polar angle θ are presented in Fig. 3, namely, the experimental data corrected for reconstruction and conversion efficiency, MC predictions for non-direct (back-

Fig. 2. (a) Energy distributions of soft photons in the angular range of 0–20 mrad; (b) same with background subtracted and fit curves superimposed.

ground) γ 's, and predictions for the inner hadronic bremsstrahlung (note, the latter does not present a *theoretical*³ angular distribution, being smeared by MC procedure involving experimental resolution). The distributions are plotted for two energy bands: 0.2–0.5 GeV and 0.5–1 GeV.

It can be seen from these plots that the excess of observed photons over the background is larger at small angles, behaving similarly to the hadronic

³ A *theoretical* angular distribution is much narrower, having a maximum (in our case of 280 GeV/c π^-p interactions) at about 0.5 mrad.

Fig. 3. Angular distributions of soft photons. (a) Experimental data and MC predictions for background γ 's and bremsstrahlung for $0.2 < E_\gamma < 0.5 \text{ GeV}$; (b) same with background subtracted; (c), (d) same as (a), (b) but for $0.5 < E_\gamma < 1 \text{ GeV}$.

bremstrahlung, and decreases in absolute value at wider angles. However, it is difficult to conclude what is the behaviour of the photon excess at wide angles where the signal (anomalous photons + inner bremsstrahlung) is small and the hadronic background is large while the systematic errors for the data and background are of the order of 10–12%, as in our case. It follows from this that the investigation of the anomalous photons at wide polar angles (say, at $\theta > 50$ mrad) requires a reduction of systematic errors in the data and background down to 2–3% (even merely to establish the presence of the direct photons) which is a difficult task (see, e.g., [14]).

At small angles (below 20 mrad) we compared the experimental characteristics of the soft photon signal presented here, i.e., for the data of the experiment WA91, with those reported in [15] (see Figs. 3 and 4 therein) for the data of the experiment WA83, which studied the same channel (inclusive production of soft photons in $\pi^- p$ interactions at 280 GeV/c) using a calorimetric method [5]. We find that they are in good agreement.

6. Conclusion

The characteristics of the anomalous soft photon radiation observed in $\pi^- p$ interactions at 280 GeV/c show features similar to those predicted for inner hadronic bremsstrahlung, excepting the absolute photon rate. The ratio of the observed signal to the expected inner bremsstrahlung is re-calculated to be 5.3 ± 1.0 .

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References

- [1] L.D. Landau, I.Ya. Pomeranchuk, Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR 92 (1953) 535;
L.D. Landau, I.Ya. Pomeranchuk, Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR 92 (1953) 735.
- [2] F. Low, Phys. Rev. 110 (1958) 150.
- [3] P.V. Chliapnikov, et al., Phys. Lett. B 141 (1984) 276.
- [4] F. Botterweck, et al., Z. Phys. C 51 (1991) 541.
- [5] S. Banerjee, et al., Phys. Lett. B 305 (1993) 182.
- [6] V. Balek, N. Pisutova, J. Pisut, Acta Phys. Pol. B 21 (1990) 149.
- [7] P. Lichard, Phys. Rev. D 50 (1994) 6824.
- [8] A. Belogianni, et al., Phys. Lett. B 408 (1997) 487.
- [9] A. Belogianni, et al., Phys. Lett. B 548 (2002) 129.
- [10] J.C. Lassalle, F. Carena, S. Pensotti, Nucl. Instrum. Methods 176 (1980) 371.
- [11] B. Andersson, G. Gustafson, N. Almquist, Nucl. Phys. B 281 (1987) 289.
- [12] W.R. Wilson, H. Mirayama, Q.W.O. Rogers, SLAC preprint SLAC-265, 1985.
- [13] J. Haissinski, LAL (Orsay) preprint LAL 87-11, 1987.
- [14] J. Antos, et al., Z. Phys. C 59 (1993) 547.
- [15] T.J. Brodbeck, Some aspects of anomalous soft photon production in $\pi^- p$ interactions at 280 GeV, in: A. Bialas, K. Fialkowski, K. Zalewski, R.C. Hwa (Eds.), Proc. Cracow Workshop on Multiparticle Production, Soft Physics and Fluctuations, Cracow, May 1993, World Scientific, Singapore, 1994, p. 63.